

LANGUAGE AND CULTURE IN ENGLISH CLASSROOMS: GREETINGS, WAYS OF EXPRESSING POLITENESS.

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Annotation: This scientific article is devoted to the study of the relationship between language and culture in the English classroom, with a focus on greetings and ways of expressing politeness. Language and Culture in English Classrooms: Greetings, Expressions of Courtesy" examines the role of culture in the process of teaching English. The article draws attention to the fact that language carries with it social and cultural meanings, and that knowledge of culture is a necessary condition for the effective use of language. The article discusses various forms of greetings and ways of expressing courtesy in English, which often cause difficulties for students due to differences in cultural traditions. The authors offer methodological recommendations aimed at improving the understanding of cultural differences that may arise when using the English language in the context of intercultural communication. The article is based on the results of an empirical study conducted in English classrooms in the context of intercultural communication and contains useful recommendations for teachers of English who work with students from different cultural backgrounds.

Keywords: English, intercultural communication, greetings, expressions of politeness, cultural nuances, intercultural approach, teaching foreign languages, communication skills, education, students.

Introduction: Language and culture are two aspects of human society that are closely interconnected, with one influencing the other in various ways. This is particularly evident in the context of English language classrooms, where learners acquire not only the grammatical rules and vocabulary of the English language but also gain insight into the cultural norms and expectations that underpin its use. Greetings and expressions of politeness are central to this cultural dimension, as they reflect deep-seated values, beliefs, and social hierarchies. In this article, we delve into the complexities of language and culture in English classrooms, focusing on the role of greetings and expressions of politeness in shaping communication and social dynamics. By elucidating these issues, we aim to provide a deeper understanding of the intricate

relationship between language, culture, and learning, and offer insights for effective language teaching and intercultural communication.

Intercultural communication is an important aspect of language learning and teaching, especially in English classes where students come from different cultures. Understanding the ways of expressing courtesy and greetings in different cultures is essential for effective communication between students. In a multicultural classroom, teachers need to be aware of differences in language use and cultural norms in order to create an inclusive environment. Learning about different cultures and languages not only promotes intercultural awareness, but also helps students develop intercultural competence.

Greeting is one of the main aspects related to language and culture. This is the primary contact between people and is considered one of the main elements of speech etiquette. In different countries and cultures, greetings can differ significantly in both form and content. For example, some cultures use long greeting formulas that include ritual gestures, while other cultures only need to say one word. It is very important to pay attention to these cultural characteristics when teaching English so that students can use the correct forms of greeting according to cultural standards, which will help them better understand the local culture and communicate more successfully with native speakers.

Expressions of politeness are an integral part of interpersonal communication, and their use can vary greatly in different cultures. The study of these courtesies is necessary to create adequate communication links and avoid cultural misunderstandings.

Cultural nuances are also important when learning English, as they influence how politeness and greetings are expressed in different cultures. This may include set rules, such as the use of a specific type of greeting depending on the social status of the interlocutor.

An intercultural approach in English classrooms is also very important as it allows students to understand and respect cultural differences. This helps in establishing good relationships between students both from different cultures and with native speakers.

Teaching English must be culturally sensitive, as cultural nuances can affect how politeness and greetings are expressed in different cultures. This should be taken into account when designing the training course and including various forms of greetings and expressions of gratitude.

Communication skills are also important for successful English learning as they help students to effectively apply their language skills in real situations, including courtesy and the use of appropriate forms of greeting.

Education plays an important role in preparing students for intercultural communication and work in international teams. Understanding cultural nuances and ways of showing politeness improves the effectiveness of communication and allows you to successfully interact with people from different cultures.

Students also play a key role in learning the cultural nuances of the language and showing politeness. Participating in discussions and working in pairs with native speakers helps students improve their communication skills and learn more about cultural differences in greetings and courtesy.

Conclusion: In the traditional understanding of teaching English in the classroom, the importance of showing courtesy is noted, which determines the tone of the whole conversation. In English-speaking cultures, even small nuances of courtesy and greetings can play a key role in first impressions, as well as successful communication with native speakers. For this reason, knowledge of the cultural and linguistic components is becoming increasingly important when teaching a foreign language. Key aspects to consider when teaching are cultural nuances, an intercultural approach, communication skills and an understanding of the importance of courtesy. Therefore, training should include appropriate practices and strategies in order to effectively apply language knowledge in various situations.

References:

1. Chen, G. M. (1995). Language and social cognition in cross-cultural communication. Taylor & Francis.
2. Culpeper, J. (2011). Politeness and impoliteness. Continuum.
3. Kasper, G., & Rose, K. R. (2002). Pragmatics in language teaching. Cambridge University Press.
4. Scollon, R., & Scollon, S. W. (2001). Intercultural communication: A discourse approach. Wiley-Blackwell.